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International Journal of Educational Research

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/ijedures

Do task type and partner role matter? An experience sampling study on the perceived benefit of teacher collaboration in Swiss primary schools

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Teacher collaboration
 Collaboration benefit
 Special needs teachers
 Experience sampling
 Multilevel model with categorical predictors
 Tasks in teacher collaboration

ABSTRACT

Collaboration, an essential part of teachers' professional practice, has significant potential to enhance student learning by improving instructional quality through professional learning. However, research findings on such benefits are not consistent. This study examined the specific tasks teachers collaborate on during non-instructional work time as well as the perceived benefit of their collaboration using an experience sampling method. 5625 collaborative activities among regular teachers and between regular teachers and special needs teachers in primary schools in Switzerland were analyzed. We used multilevel models to compare the perceived benefits of different task types in collaborative activities. Our key findings are: First, collaboration involved nearly the same amount of administrative and pedagogical tasks for the school (secondary tasks) as for the class (primary tasks). Second, teachers perceived primary tasks as more beneficial than secondary tasks. Third, collaboration between regular teachers and special needs teachers predominantly focused on primary tasks, mostly related to individual student support, and only little on instructional planning. Fourth, no significant difference in perceived benefit was found between collaboration among regular teachers and collaboration between regular and special needs teachers. The high frequency of secondary tasks, particularly in collaboration among regular teachers, raises questions about the overall effectiveness of teacher collaboration.

Introduction

Teacher collaboration is a central aspect of professional practice worldwide and increasingly involves not only teachers but also individuals from diverse professional backgrounds (OECD, 2019, 2024). It is associated with benefits such as teachers' professional learning (De Jong et al., 2022), teacher well-being (Muckenthaler et al., 2020), enhanced instructional quality (Goddard & Kim, 2018), and improved student outcomes (Mora-Ruano et al., 2019; Wullschleger et al., 2025). Teacher collaboration can be defined as all interactions among teachers and other school staff that relate to their professional duties (Kelchtermans, 2006) and that occur either during instructional time (e.g., co-teaching) or during non-instructional time (e.g., lesson planning, moderation of team meetings).

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2026.102993>

Received 24 March 2025; Received in revised form 23 January 2026; Accepted 14 March 2026

Available online 31 March 2026

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However, evidence regarding the benefits of teacher collaboration remains inconclusive as positive effects have not been observed consistently (Vangrieken et al., 2015). Collaboration can even be experienced negatively as a source of tension (Weddle et al., 2019) or a waste of time (Johnson, 2003). Teachers perceive collaboration in formal professional development settings more positively when they negotiate diverse professional perspectives within supportive relationships (Gast et al., 2017) and engage in tasks directly applicable to classroom practice (Camburn & Han, 2017; Hattie, 2023). However, studies on everyday teacher collaboration outside professional development settings have not yet systematically examined a broad set of task types, collaboration partners, and their associated benefits.

We identified three critical aspects that are frequently overlooked in researching the benefits of teacher collaboration. First, studies on teacher collaboration often focus on primary tasks, or tasks that are closely connected to day-to-day teaching (e.g., planning lessons and supporting students). They therefore neglect the fact that teachers' responsibilities in many countries extend beyond primary tasks to include secondary tasks. Secondary tasks are not directly tied to classroom instruction but concern administrative or pedagogical responsibilities at the team or school level (e.g., coordinating break duty or preparing reports for school evaluation; OECD, 2024). It is important to separate primary and secondary tasks in empirical studies on teacher collaboration, as the ratio between primary and secondary tasks might be an important factor in determining whether collaboration is beneficial for teachers' professional learning, well-being, instructional quality, and student learning (Maag Merki et al., 2022; Rechsteiner et al., 2025).

Second, teacher collaboration is increasingly multiprofessional, including various school staff. Among them, special needs teachers are one of the most important collaboration partners alongside regular teachers (Paulsrud & Nilholm, 2023). Collaboration during non-instructional time among regular teachers may differ from collaboration with special needs teachers, as the latter often leads to or follows co-teaching during instructional time in one class (Solis et al. 2012). Furthermore, variations in knowledge, roles, and responsibilities between regular teachers and special needs teachers may either foster shared knowledge construction or, by generating conflict, constrain it, thereby shaping the benefits of collaborative efforts. However, most studies on teacher collaboration do not differentiate between the specific roles of collaboration partners.

The third relevant aspect is methodology. When examining teacher collaboration, researchers have mostly used retrospective and cross-sectional methods (Lecat et al., 2020; Weddle, 2022). However, these methods are often less valid because they are prone to retrospective and response bias (Myin-Germeys & Kubbens, 2022). For this reason, Fritz et al. (2023) proposed using the interval-contingent experience sampling method to collect information on teachers' everyday collaborative activities, in which data is gathered daily at predefined time points over a certain period. The approach minimizes memory bias, makes it possible to collect accurate information on experiences related to specific activities, and does not interfere with teachers' normal daily routines (Maag Merki & Grob et al., 2022; Zirkel et al., 2015).

The aim of this study is therefore to shed light on the frequency of the different task types that primary school teachers collaboratively address during their non-instructional work time. We further aim to examine how often these tasks occur in collaboration among regular teachers compared to collaboration between regular and special needs teachers. Finally, we analyze teachers' perception of the benefit of these collaborative activities. In doing so, we seek to inform future research, policymakers, school leaders, and teachers about how collaborative resources during non-instructional time are currently used and might be used more effectively to support meaningful professional learning while avoiding unnecessary increases in teachers' workload.

Literature review

From the perspective of schools as learning communities, teacher collaboration is theorized to influence student learning through a central mechanism: the shared construction of new knowledge, which leads to improved instruction and, in turn, to better student outcomes (Mitchell & Sackney, 2011). Mitchell and Sackney emphasize that the meaning and purpose of the content on which knowledge is constructed are essential for effective professional learning, as they help capture attention, foster motivation, and stimulate imagination. For teachers, tasks that relate closely to their everyday challenges in teaching and supporting students are considered most meaningful (James et al., 2007). The construction of new knowledge might further benefit from the negotiation of multiple perspectives (Mitchell & Sackney, 2011), which may arise when professionals with different knowledge bases, such as regular teachers and special needs teachers, collaborate.

Following this argument, the literature review proceeds in five steps. First, we define teacher collaboration to establish a common understanding of the concept (2.1). Second, we examine research on the types of tasks teachers engage in during their non-instructional work time to establish a categorization scheme for the tasks on which teachers collaborate (2.2). Third, we highlight research on how differences in professional roles and knowledge bases, particularly between regular teachers and special needs teachers, may influence collaboration outcomes (2.3). Fourth, we review empirical evidence on the outcomes of teacher collaboration to clarify how the subjectively perceived benefit can serve as valid indicator for effective teacher collaboration (2.4). Finally, we present our research questions and hypotheses (2.5).

2.1. Teacher collaboration

For this study, we base our definition of teacher collaboration on Kelchtermans (2006) and Wullschleger et al. (2019), who describe teacher collaboration as at least two teachers doing things together to perform their professional duties. Given that teachers collaborate not only with other regular teachers but also with other educational staff members at a school (Borg & Drange, 2019), we define teacher collaboration as a teacher's interaction with at least one other school professional for professional duties-related purposes.

Teacher collaboration varies across multiple dimensions. It may take place during instructional work time, when teachers are co-

teaching students, or during non-instructional work time, that is, time outside of lesson hours without students (OECD, 2024). Collaboration during non-instructional work time may either prepare for or follow up on co-teaching scenarios, in which teachers jointly instruct students (Friend et al., 2010), or relate to teaching where each teacher is responsible for a separate class. Teacher collaboration also unfolds in both formal settings, such as scheduled meetings, and informal settings, such as spontaneous conversations during breaks (Kyndt et al., 2016). The modus of collaboration can range from the relatively superficial level—such as sharing materials or splitting tasks—to more integrative practices like synchronizing lesson plans and co-constructing instruction or student support (Gräsel et al., 2006). Furthermore, interactions vary in their conversational features, which can either foster or hinder professional learning (Lefstein et al., 2020). Finally, teacher collaboration can be distinguished by the diversity of collaboration partners in terms of roles and professional backgrounds (Borg & Drange, 2019), as well as by the task type, which may range from administrative responsibilities to pedagogical work concerning the teacher's own class, their team, or the entire school.

Until now, however, very few studies on teacher collaboration have differentiated between the broad range of task types on which teachers collaborate. Those that do tend to focus narrowly on tasks related to teachers' primary tasks, such as instruction, assessment, or individual student support (e.g., Ronfeldt et al., 2015). These studies overlook the fact that, during their non-instructional work time, teachers engage in a much broader range of tasks (OECD, 2024).

2.2. The task in teacher collaboration

The OECD *Teaching and Learning International Survey* (TALIS), the OECD *Education at a Glance* (EAG) report, and the professional mandate by the Swiss Teachers' Association (LCH) examined and categorized the wide range of tasks that teachers perform during their non-instructional work time (OECD, 2019, 2024).

Mainly five categories of tasks teachers perform in their non-instructional time can be identified: (1) instructional tasks, (2) individual support tasks, (3) administrative tasks for the class, (4) pedagogical tasks for teams and the school, and (5) administrative tasks for the team and the school. Instructional tasks involve planning, preparing, and further developing lessons for the whole class. Individual support tasks refer to the planning, preparation, and further development of support for individual students. Administrative tasks for the class include all organizational and administrative duties that are not pedagogical in nature but are necessary for the functioning of school life, such as writing information letters, creating schedules, or organizing class outings.

We define categories 1, 2, and 3 above as primary tasks. James et al. (2007) found that teachers see these tasks as their main concern. Teachers frame primary tasks as "ensuring effective and enriched teaching for learning for all pupils and improving and further enriching teaching and learning for all pupils" (p. 546).

In categories 4 and 5 above, teachers take on a variety of tasks that extend beyond their primary class responsibilities; we frame these as secondary tasks. The EAG report shows that they can encompass a wide range of responsibilities (OECD, 2024): Teachers engage in school management by contributing to the development, implementation, and evaluation of school policies, serving on administrative boards, or leading subject-specific or grade-level teaching teams. Additionally, teachers play a crucial role in organizing school events, planning extracurricular programs, and supervising students during these activities. The EAG also reported that some teachers act as mentors or trainers for student teachers and newly hired educators. They are involved in designing or coordinating professional development programs for teams or the entire school. Moreover, they take on responsibilities in resource management, such as overseeing gym, library, or workshop resources and designing and maintaining learning environments for a team or the entire school. In some cases, teachers take on specialized roles, such as serving as ICT coordinators.

As Thompson et al. (2022) argues, the growing partition of these secondary tasks during teachers' non-instructional work time might be closely tied to the dual pressures of school autonomy and accountability. The school autonomy and accountability policy model has been adopted in numerous countries around the world (Verger et al., 2024). With increased autonomy, schools have a responsibility to self-improve and self-manage, which inherently requires more active participation from teachers in managerial and administrative roles. At the same time, accountability frameworks demand measurable outcomes; this necessitates detailed documentation, evaluation, and reporting—processes that frequently fall under these secondary tasks. Data from TALIS 2018 shows that across OECD countries, teachers spend approximately 10% of their non-instructional work time on secondary tasks. When the supervision of students in extracurricular activities is included, this increases to around 25% (OECD, 2019). These secondary tasks can detract from teachers' core responsibilities and be seen as unbeneficial or lead to higher levels of stress (OECD, 2020; Heffernan et al., 2022; Creagh et al., 2023; Stacey et al., 2023). However, research on the frequency of different task types in teacher collaboration is still very limited. TALIS 2018, for instance, only differentiated between tasks related to instructional purposes, such as providing feedback, exchanging teaching materials, or discussing specific students. The results showed that deeper forms of collaboration, such as providing feedback or conducting classroom observations, are less prevalent than simpler exchanges like exchanging materials (OECD, 2019). To our knowledge, little is known about how task types are distributed in non-instructional collaboration among regular teachers, or how this distribution varies with the professional role of the collaboration partner. This role may also shape the effectiveness of collaboration for professional learning, as the involved knowledge bases require more joint negotiation. In the next chapter, we will focus on one of the most important roles of a collaboration partner next to other regular teachers.

2.3. Special needs teachers as important collaboration partners

Teachers engage in collaboration not only with their fellow regular teachers but also with a variety of other professionals in the school environment, such as special needs teachers, speech-language and movement therapists, school psychologists, and principals (Borg & Drange, 2019; Vogt et al., 2022). One of the most important of these collaboration partners in context of inclusive school

systems is the special needs teacher (Mulholland & O'Connor, 2016; Hansen et al., 2020). Researchers argue that frequent collaboration between regular teachers and special needs teachers is essential for functioning inclusive school systems (Alabdallat et al., 2021; Hedegaard-Soerensen et al., 2018). Special needs teachers are educational experts (often former teachers) who have formal training in assisting children with various learning, mental, emotional, and physical challenges. Their roles include teaching, assisting regular teachers through supporting and consulting, diagnosing learning differences, and creating individualized support plans (Paulsrud & Nilholm, 2023). Regular teachers often collaborate with special needs teachers in a dyadic partnership (Jurkowski & Müller, 2018).

Collaboration between regular teachers and special needs teachers during non-instructional time may differ from collaboration among regular teachers. When teachers and special needs teachers collaborate during non-instructional time, collaboration often follows or leads to co-teaching scenarios (Solis et al., 2012), which might favor collaboration focusing on primary tasks like instruction and individual student support. However, as with collaborative activities among regular teachers, little is known about the distribution of different tasks in collaborative activities between regular teachers and special needs teachers.

Further, general teachers might experience collaboration with special needs teachers differently, as it could be more challenging due to their different educational backgrounds and roles, which may result in differing focuses or values in the context of teaching (Da Fonte & Barton-Arwood, 2017). In a review of qualitative studies, Paulsrud and Nilholm (2023) found that these differences have the potential to improve instructional strategies and enhance classroom inclusivity. However, they also noted a potential for unproductive conflict.

Empirical evidence remains limited regarding the positive or differential effects of collaboration between regular teachers and special needs teachers on teachers' professional learning, instructional practices, or student outcomes (Grosche & Moser Opitz, 2023). While evidence on collaboration between regular and special needs teachers remains limited, numerous studies have examined the broader positive and negative outcomes of teacher collaboration. Several of these studies suggest that the subjectively perceived benefit of collaboration can serve as a reliable indicator of its effectiveness. In the next chapter we will focus on perceived benefit as an important indicator for effective teacher collaboration.

2.4. Perceived benefit of teacher collaboration

Teacher collaboration is positively associated with a range of outcomes, including emotional relief (Muckenthaler et al., 2020), professional learning (Tallman, 2021), instructional quality (Methlagl, 2022; Goddard & Kim, 2018), and student achievement (Mora-Ruano et al., 2019). However, others have also identified potential drawbacks, such as increased workload and stress (Johnson, 2003; Rechsteiner et al., 2025), risks of groupthink and burnout contagion (Kaihoi et al., 2022), or a loss of professional autonomy (Meredith et al., 2022). Several studies have emphasized that the subjectively perceived benefit of collaborative efforts is a crucial indicator of whether collaboration successfully produces positive effects: (Wullschleger et al., 2025) demonstrated that teachers who experienced their collaboration as beneficial demonstrated greater improvements in instructional quality, which in turn predicted gains in student achievement. Similarly, Sinnema et al. (2021) found that teachers who perceived discussions with colleagues as beneficial reported more substantial improvements in professional practice, such as increased experimentation. Ronfeldt et al. (2015) further found that students of teachers who engaged in collaboration they perceived as more beneficial achieved higher learning gains compared to students of teachers involved in collaboration they perceived as less beneficial. Additionally, Ronfeldt et al. (2015) determined that the perceived benefit of teacher collaboration varies depending on the type of task teachers collaborated on. Collaboration on assessment has been found to be the strongest predictor, followed by collaboration on addressing student needs and on instruction planning (Ronfeldt et al., 2015). However, while Ronfeldt et al. differentiated between task types closely related to teachers' primary tasks, they did not account for the broader range of task types outlined in Section 2.2. To date, it remains unclear to what extent teachers collaborate on these different task types and how beneficial they perceive such tasks to be. The degree to which collaborative tasks are aligned with teachers' primary responsibilities may serve as an important indicator explaining why teacher collaboration has shown mixed effects.

2.5. Research questions

We identified three notable research gaps, regarding: (1) thorough exploration of the diverse tasks in which teachers engage in collaborative activities during non-instructional work time, (2) differentiation between regular teachers' collaboration with other regular teachers or with special needs teachers, and (3) whether different task types and collaboration partners differ in terms of benefit perceived by teachers.

We therefore focused on the following research questions (RQ):

RQ1a: What are the frequencies of different task types in regular teachers' collaborative activities during non-instructional work time?

RQ1b: How do these frequencies differ between collaborative activities among regular teachers and collaborative activities between regular teachers and special needs teachers?

RQ2a: What collaborative activities do regular teachers perceive as the most beneficial, considering type of task?

RQ2b: What collaborative activities do regular teachers perceive as the most beneficial, considering whether the collaboration is with other regular teachers or with special needs teachers?

For research question 2a, we hypothesized that collaborative activities focusing on tasks closer to teachers' primary task (e.g., preparing and following up lessons) are perceived as more beneficial than collaboration focusing on secondary tasks, which are more distal to instruction and students' learning (e.g., pedagogical tasks for the school) (e.g. Creagh et al., 2023). As there is limited previous

research available on the differences between collaboration among regular teachers and regular teachers' collaboration with special needs teachers, we did not hypothesize a specific direction of effects on perceived benefit and approached research question 2b in an exploratory manner.

4. Method

4.1. Study design

To address the research questions, we employed an interval-contingent experience sampling method (ESM) to collect data on teachers' daily collaborative tasks. Interval-contingent sampling refers to an assessment schedule in which data collection is initiated at preselected timepoints (Fritz et al., 2023). In our study, data were gathered from Monday to Sunday over three non-consecutive weeks during the 2019/20 school year: one week each in November, December, and January (see Fig. 1). Each measurement week was separated by a three- to four-week interval to capture variation across different types of weeks (i.e., a regular week in November, an intense pre-Christmas week, and a demanding week prior to report deadlines). Every day during each measurement week the participants received a push notification at 5 pm. on their smartphones or via email and were then prompted to complete an online logbook within the next 24 h.

This method helps reduce retrospective bias, minimizes the influence of decision heuristics, and encourages spontaneous responses. However, it still relies on participants' subjective perceptions and their honesty, which may introduce bias due to social desirability—although this bias might be attenuated by the proximity of the measurement to the actual events (Zirkel et al., 2015).

Prior to participating in the ESM part of the study, in September 2019 the participants completed an online questionnaire covering teacher demographics and other characteristics at the school and individual level.

The daily online logbook had the following structure: First, participants were asked if they had worked that day and, if yes, how many lessons they had taught. If they had worked, they documented all activities they had engaged in during their non-instructional work time for that day. For each activity, participants first selected from a list of 15 predefined tasks in a multiple-choice format (e.g., preparing and following up on lessons, organizational/administrative work for a team; see Fig. 2 for a full overview). Additionally, for each activity, participants specified whether they did the activity alone or in collaboration with others. They could choose as many collaborators as needed from a list of 13 predefined options (e.g., special needs teachers, principals). They then detailed the duration of the activity. Last, they had to rate each activity based on how beneficial they perceived it to be. After they had added one activity in this manner, they were asked if they had another activity to record. They could document as many activities with any combination of tasks and collaborators per day as they wanted. The study design resulted in nested data with information on teacher (e.g., age) and activity level (e.g., tasks and benefit) (See Appendix A2 for an example).

4.2. Sample

To recruit participants, we contacted primary schools in the German-speaking part of Switzerland through cantonal representatives and various education associations. If a school expressed interest in participating, the principal was required to discuss participation with the entire school. Participation was only possible with the consent of all school staff. To encourage participation, each school was promised a report comparing its data with that of other schools in the sample. In addition, each participating school received a compensation of 100 Swiss francs (CHF) for their staff room coffee fund.

We collected data by questioning all school staff in primary schools across different regions of Switzerland. All participants took part voluntarily and provided active informed consent before participating in the study. Our sampling strategy resulted in a starting sample of 32,018 activities of 1283 school staff members in 57 schools in 14 cantons of Switzerland.

As our primary interest lay in understanding how regular teachers perceive their collaborative efforts, we included only data from

Fig. 1. Data Collection.

Recording of workday XY

1 Did you work today? (Yes, or No; Survey stops here if a teacher had not worked that day)

2 Did you teach today? (Yes: _____ number of lessons, or No)

Recording of an activity on workday XY

3 What was the activity about? (you can choose multiple contents per activity)

Instruction Tasks (IT)

- Preparing and following up on lessons (including excursions and special events), correcting, assessing (PL)
- Reflecting on and further developing own teaching/work (RT)
- Reflecting on and further developing my own skills as a teacher/professional (RS)

Individual Support Tasks (IST)

- Individual student support planning (IS)
- Reflecting on and further developing support for individual students (RIS)

Organizational and Administrative Tasks for the Class (OATC)

- Organizational and administrative tasks for own class or individual students (OAC)
- Reflecting on and further developing organizational and administrative work (ROAC)

Pedagogical Tasks for the Team and the School (PTTS)

- Pedagogical tasks for a team (PT)
- Reflecting on and further developing pedagogical tasks for a team (RPT)
- Pedagogical tasks for the school (PS)
- Reflecting on and further developing pedagogical tasks for the school (RPS)

Organizational and Administrative Tasks for the Team and the School (OATTS)

- Organizational and administrative tasks for a team (OAT)
- Reflecting on and further developing organizational and administrative tasks for a team (ROAT)
- Organizational and administrative tasks for the school (OAS)
- Reflecting on and further developing organizational and administrative tasks for the school (ROAS)

4 Did you do this activity alone or with someone else?

- Alone
- Student(s)
- Parent(s) or legal guardian(s)
- Other teaching and specialist staff within my school (RT)
- Steering committee
- School administration
- Entire school team
- Specialist(s) in special needs education (SNT)
- Specialist(s) in German as a Second Language
- Therapist(s) (e.g., speech therapy)
- Specialist(s) in school social work
- School psychologist(s)
- Teaching/specialist staff outside of my school
- School authorities

5 How long did this activity take?

Minutes, in 10-minute steps

Hours, in 1-hour steps

6 How beneficial was this activity?

Scale from 1 = not at all beneficial to 4 = very beneficial

Fig. 2. Daily Logbook to Collect Non-Instructional Activities and Perceived Benefit.

regular teachers who had no additional roles, such as part-time special needs teaching, acting as principals, or other specialist functions. In Switzerland, regular teachers are either class teachers, who teach multiple school subjects and manage the main responsibilities for a single class, or single-subject teachers, who specialize in teaching a specific academic subject across different groups of students.

Further, for validity, we included only data from any teacher who responded to at least 50% of the daily prompts. Responding to a prompt meant simply answering “yes” or “no” to the initial question of whether they had worked that day (Fig. 2). We reasoned that if a participant responded to fewer than 10 prompts, it was likely that they did not participate adequately, making these entries untrustworthy. This reduced the sample to 21,385 activities of 821 regular teachers.

Next, of all the activities of these regular teachers we excluded activities done by a teacher alone and activities that included

collaboration with pupils or parents as we were only interested in the collaboration of regular teachers with other teachers and school professionals. Thus, our final sample consisted of 5625 collaborative activities of 596 regular teachers in 56 schools. Missing data analysis revealed that the final sample did not significantly differ from the baseline sample of regular teachers in terms of gender and age. However, participants in the final sample were more likely to have an employment rate higher than 75%.

As teachers could choose multiple task options per recorded activity, the collaborative activities contained between 1 and 15 different task options ($M = 1.80$, $SD = 1.49$). The collaborative activities lasted on average 75.15 min ($SD = 79.60$, 10–530). Collaborative activities with other regular teachers lasted on average 65.53 min ($SD = 67.42$, 10–530) and contained on average 1.69 tasks ($SD = 1.34$, 1–11) per collaborative activity. Collaborative activities with special needs teachers as collaboration partners contained on average 1.74 tasks ($SD = 1.28$, 1–11) and had a mean duration of 49.54 min ($SD = 57.15$, 10–530).

The participating regular teachers were on average 41.33 years old ($SD = 11.83$, 21–67); 85.23% were women; they had on average 16.30 years' ($SD = 11.41$, 0–44) teaching experience; 58.56% had an employment rate higher than 75%; 26.34% worked as a single-subject teacher, and 73.66% had main class responsibilities. On average, the 596 participants reported 9.44 collaborative activities ($SD = 6.27$, 1–43) during the three weeks of the survey. The age and gender distributions in the final sample matched those of the teacher population in Switzerland (Federal Statistical Office, 2024).

4.3. Measures

To capture collaboration activities as closely as possible to everyday practice, teachers had the flexibility to report any combination of tasks and collaboration partners across multiple non-instructional activities by answering four questions for each activity: (1) tasks involved, (2) whether they worked alone or with others, (3) duration of the activity, and (4) assessment of the activity's benefits. Teachers repeated this process until they had recorded all their activities during non-instructional work time on that day.

Tasks in collaborative activities

To record each non-instructional activity, teachers could choose from 15 predefined tasks (Fig. 2). The predefined tasks were based on the professional mandate of Swiss teachers (LCH, 2014; Feller et al., 2020). The task options were further validated and refined in a pilot study (Maag Merki, Grob et al., 2022). However, the freedom to combine 15 predefined tasks (Fig. 2) in one activity resulted in 591 unique combinations of tasks in an activity. To reduce this complexity and arrive at a comparable and interpretable set of task categories, we applied three different categorization schemes (see Appendices A1 and A2 for a visual representation).

First, we grouped the 15 task options into five categories (Fig. 2): instruction tasks (IT), individual support tasks (IST), organizational and administrative tasks for the class (OATC), pedagogical tasks for the team or the school (PTTS), and organizational and administrative tasks for the team or the school (OATTS).

Second, we assigned each recorded activity to these five task categories. However, as an activity could contain tasks from different categories, an activity could be assigned to more than one of the categories. For instance, if a teacher indicated that a collaborative activity involved reflection on and development of their own teaching (a task in category IT) as well as pedagogical tasks for the team (category PTTS), this activity would be classified under both IT and PTTS. When analyzing the frequency of these five categories, their non-mutual exclusivity was not an issue.

For research question 2, which involved comparing the perceived benefit of different task categories, mutually exclusive categories were required. To address this, we decided to use two different categorizations of the 15 task options. First, we grouped the activities into three broader ones: primary tasks (activities with tasks in IT, IST, OATC), secondary tasks (activities with tasks in PTTS, OATTS), and mixed tasks (those that contain tasks in both primary and secondary tasks). For example, if an activity included tasks in both IT and IST, it was categorized as a primary task. However, if it included tasks in the categories IT and PTTS, it was categorized as a mixed task. These three broader categories were mutually exclusive, meaning no activity assigned to one of these categories could be classified under the other two.

To gain finer grained insights, we aimed to compare the perceived benefits of the five more detailed categories. As these categories were not mutually exclusive and because of that not comparable in multilevel models, we decided to hierarchically assign the activities to the five categories based on their proximity to the teacher's primary responsibilities (James et al., 2007; LCH, 2014; Schleicher, 2012). The hierarchical assignment followed this order: instructional task (IT^h), individual support tasks (IST^h), organizational and administrative task for the class (OATC^h), pedagogical task for the team or the school (PTTS^h), and organizational and administrative tasks for the team or the school (OATTS^h). For example, if a participant selected tasks from categories IST, OATC, and PTTS within a single activity, that activity was assigned to category IST^h. This hierarchical approach enabled us to compare the five categories in multilevel models. However, this approach had two limitations that should be considered when interpreting the results. First, it introduced a bias in frequency, favoring activities higher up in the hierarchy. Second, these task categories included either pure activities (tasks from a single category) or mixed activities (tasks from other categories lower in the hierarchy).

In summary, we used three types of categorizations: the three mutually exclusive categories, the five non-mutually exclusive categories, and the hierarchically assigned five categories. Types one and two were analyzed for research question 1 and types one and three were included in multilevel models for research question 2 (see Appendix A1 and A2 for a full overview of the categorization process).

Collaboration partner

For each recorded activity, participants also indicated whether they completed it alone or in collaboration with others, choosing from 13 options (Fig. 2). Our analysis focused specifically on two collaborations: collaboration with other regular teachers (RT) and

collaboration with special needs teachers (SNT). The rest of the collaborative activities were classified as collaborative activities with other school staff and combinations (OT) and not analyzed in more detail. Each activity was dummy coded with one of these three categories.

Benefit of collaborative activities

For each activity, teachers had to give a rating from 1 to 4 in response to the question “How beneficial was this activity?” (German: *Wie ergiebig war diese Tätigkeit?*). This instrument was pretested in 2018 with 64 teachers from four secondary schools in German-speaking Switzerland. In subsequent on-site workshops, participants provided feedback and revealed a shared understanding of the term *ergiebig* (beneficial), consistently associating it with the usefulness and productivity of a task. Notably, the question did not specify what the activity was beneficial for, leaving us to infer that the teacher assessed the benefit based on their immediate concerns. These concerns could relate to the tasks involved in the activity itself or to broader educational goals. Although this single-item measure had limitations in terms of depth, it still provided insight into how beneficial teachers perceived an activity to be in relation to their priorities. As Ronfeldt et al. (2015) and Wullschleger and Maag Merki (2025) have shown, such perceptions can be predictive of more effective teacher collaboration.

Covariates

As covariates, we included the number of tasks in one activity and the duration of the activity in minutes. Both served as indicators of high mental load in an activity, which may influence the perceived benefit of a collaborative activity. The Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) model by Bakker and Demerouti (2007) states that too high demands not compensated by sufficient resources can lead to more strain and less motivation and potentially reduce perceived benefit. However, when sufficient resources (e.g., time autonomy, clear roles) are present, more tasks in one activity or lengthy activities could also increase perceived benefit.

4.4. Data analysis

Due to the sampling design, the data appeared in a nested structure with two levels: categorized collaborative activities at Level 1, nested within individual teachers at Level 2. For research question 1, we decided to analyze the frequencies of all collaborative activities on Level 1, ignoring the fact that some teachers may have contributed significantly more collaborative activities than others, as we were only interested in what kind of collaborative activities generally occur and how often. We first analyzed the frequencies of the three task categories: primary tasks, secondary tasks, and mixed tasks. Second, we calculated the proportion of activities using the five more fine-grained non-mutually exclusive tasks categories. Then we repeated steps one and two with only collaborative activities among regular teachers and only collaborative activities with special needs teachers.

For our research question 2, we compared the perceived benefit of the three mutually exclusive task categories, the five mutually exclusive task categories, and the two different collaboration partners. Given that the benefit ratings of collaborative activities were nested within teachers, the perceived benefit might exhibit intercorrelation, which can lead to increased Type I errors and biased parameter estimates (Nezlek, 2020; Peugh, 2010). A multilevel analytic approach enabled us to properly focus on the differences between task categories and collaboration partners while controlling for variance that was explained through differences between teachers (Myin-Germeys & Kubbens, 2022).

To understand variance decomposition and assess the necessity of multilevel modeling, we first calculated the intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) of perceived benefit. The ICC indicated that 21% of the variance in the perceived benefit of collaborative activities was attributable to differences between individuals. This finding suggested a clear intercorrelation of perceived benefit, justifying the use of multilevel modeling (Hox et al., 2017).

Next, we calculated two series of multilevel models, one with the three categories and one with the five categories. In both models the categorical predictors were dummy coded. This approach allowed us to compare each task category with the others by changing the reference category. The dummy coded predictors (task types and collaboration partner) as well as the continuous covariates (number of tasks and duration of activity) were group mean centered and included as Level 1 predictors.

To ensure comparability and gain insight into within-individual effects, we transformed the outcome variable (perceived benefit) by subtracting the overall mean and dividing by the Level 1 residual standard deviation. This transformation allowed the regression coefficients (β^j) to represent the expected change in the outcome (in units of the Level 1 standard deviation) associated with a change in the predictor category (Lorah, 2018; Yaremych et al., 2023).

We then constructed models following the forward-stepping procedure recommended by Hox et al. (2017). First, we estimated a null model to serve as a baseline and calculate ICC. Next, we included collaboration partner categories in the model, followed by the addition of covariates. Finally, in the first model series, we entered the three task categories; in the second model series, we included the five task categories. To obtain estimates for all differences between the categories, we changed the reference category until all comparisons were covered. We used full information maximum likelihood estimation to handle missing data (Bates et al., 2015). Marginal and conditional R^2 were calculated to represent the variance explained through the model (Lorah, 2018). All calculations were performed in R-Studio (R Core Team, 2024). For multilevel modeling we used the lme4 package (Bates et al., 2015). Appendix B presents detailed results from the two model series.

Table 1
Frequency and Perceived Benefit of the Three Categories Primary Tasks, Secondary Tasks, and Mixed Tasks.

	All activities		Collaborative		With regular teachers		With special needs teachers	
	% (n)	M (SD)	% (n) ^a	M (SD)	% (n) ^b	M (SD)	% (n) ^c	M (SD)
All tasks ^d	100 (19,439)	3.37 (0.63)	28.94 (5625)	3.33 (0.66)	54.33 (3056)	3.36 (0.64)	11.98 (674)	3.48 (0.57)
Primary tasks	70.18 (13,642)	3.41 (0.60)	46.84 (2635)	3.43 (0.62)	43.42 (1327)	3.42 (0.61)	85.46 (576)	3.47 (0.58)
Mixed tasks	9.35 (1817)	3.34 (0.62)	12.28 (691)	3.33 (0.64)	12.07 (369)	3.36 (0.60)	7.27 (49)	3.53 (0.50)
Secondary tasks	20.47 (3980)	3.22 (0.74)	40.87 (2299)	3.23 (0.71)	44.50 (1360)	3.30 (0.67)	7.27 (49)	3.49 (0.58)

Note. PT = primary tasks, MT = mixed tasks, ST = secondary tasks

^a = percentages of the three categories as partitions of the 28% collaborative activities

^b = percentages of the three categories as partitions of the 54.33% activities with regular teachers.

^c = percentages of the three categories as partitions of the 11.98% activities with special needs teachers.

^d = in column collaborative: as the percentage of all activities, in column regular teachers and special needs teachers: as percentages of all collaborative activities.

Fig. 3. Frequency of Primary Tasks, Secondary Tasks, and Mixed Tasks in all Collaborative Activities.

5. Results

5.1. Frequencies of tasks and collaboration partners

For our first research question, we explored the frequency of the different task types in regular teachers' collaboration during their non-instructional work time. Of all recorded activities, nearly one-third were done in collaboration with other regular teachers, special needs teachers, or other school professionals/in combinations. Table 1 and Fig. 3 show proportions of primary, secondary, and mixed tasks in all collaborative activities and specifically in collaborative activities among regular teachers and with special needs teachers. Overall, these results revealed that in teachers' collaborative activities, nearly as much focus was placed on secondary tasks as on primary tasks. In collaboration among regular teachers, the focus was slightly more on secondary tasks than on primary tasks. However, in collaborative activities with special needs teachers, a distinctly different picture emerged: Collaboration between regular teachers and special needs teachers primarily focused on primary tasks.

Next, we examined the frequencies of the more fine-grained five non-mutually exclusive categories across all collaborative activities. Non-mutually exclusive means that the sum of frequencies of different task types added up to >100%, as some activities included tasks from multiple task categories (see Appendix A1 and A2). Table 2 and Fig. 4 detail the distribution of these categories. Analyzing all collaborative activities without specifying the collaboration partner, we found, for example, that one-third included instructional tasks (IT).

We further found that the distribution of tasks within collaborative activities among regular teachers was similar to the distribution over all collaborative activities. In contrast, the distribution of these categories in collaboration with special needs teachers showed a different pattern: One-third included instructional tasks and nearly three fourths included individual support tasks.

Table 2 also shows the partition of activities within each of the five categories that were mixed with either secondary tasks (for IT, IST, OATC) or primary tasks (for PTTS, OATTS). For instance, 30% of all activities involving instructional tasks also included secondary tasks (either PTTS, OATTS, or both).

5.2. Perceived benefit of tasks and collaboration partners

The second research question focused on how teachers perceived the benefit of these different task categories. Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics for the frequency, mean, and standard deviation of perceived benefit across three categories: primary tasks (PT), mixed tasks (MT), and secondary tasks (ST). Appendix A3 shows descriptive statistics of the five hierarchical assigned categories.

First, we fitted a model comparing the three categories PT, MT, and ST (Table 3 and Appendix B1). Models comparing the perceived benefits of primary tasks, mixed tasks, and secondary tasks revealed that teachers perceived primary tasks as significantly more beneficial than secondary tasks. Teachers also perceived primary tasks as more beneficial than mixed tasks and mixed tasks as more beneficial than secondary tasks.

Regarding differences between collaboration partners, collaborative activities with special needs teachers were only perceived as significantly more beneficial than those among regular teachers when the task types were not included in the models (Appendix B1, B2). Further, none of the covariates, including duration of an activity and number of tasks in an activity, had a significant impact on the perceived benefit of collaborative activities.

The second series of models (Table 4 and Appendix B2), which compared the five task categories, showed a similar pattern: Teachers perceived activities in categories more closely related to teachers' primary responsibilities as more beneficial. First, when using instructional tasks (IT^h) as the reference group, we found that teachers perceived nearly all other tasks as less beneficial than IT^h.

Table 2
Frequency and Perceived Benefit of the Five Non-Mutually Exclusive Categories.

	Overall		Mixed ^d	Collaborative		Mixed ^d	With regular teachers		Mixed ^d	With special needs teachers		Mixed ^d
	% (n)	<i>M (SD)</i>	% (n)	% (n) ^a	<i>M (SD)</i>	% (n)	% (n) ^b	<i>M (SD)</i>	% (n)	% (n) ^c	<i>M (SD)</i>	% (n)
All tasks ^e	100 (19,439)	3.37 (0.63)	9.35 (1817)	28.94 (5625)	3.33 (0.66)	12.28 (691)	54.33 (3056)	3.36 (0.64)	12.07 (369)	11.98 (674)	3.48 (0.57)	7.27 (49)
IT	54.58 (10,609)	3.41 (0.58)	13.88 (1473)	31.63 (1779)	3.43 (0.61)	29.4 (523)	33.08 (1011)	3.43 (0.6)	27.79 (281)	33.23 (224)	3.54 (0.53)	14.29 (32)
IST	29.79 (5790)	3.38 (0.61)	19.93 (1154)	21.85 (1229)	3.37 (0.61)	31.9 (392)	15.58 (476)	3.39 (0.59)	21.01 (100)	71.81 (484)	3.46 (0.58)	5.58 (27)
OATC	21.79 (4235)	3.42 (0.59)	15.25 (646)	25.58 (1439)	3.42 (0.59)	16.47 (237)	23.46 (717)	3.39 (0.6)	30.13 (216)	23.00 (155)	3.44 (0.55)	16.77 (26)
PTTS	12.31 (2393)	3.27 (0.69)	40.7 (974)	25.08 (1411)	3.25 (0.69)	31.68 (447)	25.49 (779)	3.30 (0.65)	29.40 (299)	10.68 (72)	3.53 (0.5)	52.78 (38)
OATTS	22.83 (4438)	3.25 (0.71)	30.49 (1353)	39.29 (2210)	3.25 (0.69)	21.58 (477)	42.05 (1285)	3.32 (0.66)	20.62 (265)	6.38 (43)	3.40 (0.58)	48.84 (21)

Note. IT = instructional tasks, IST = individual support tasks, OATC = organizational and administrative tasks for teacher's own class, PTTS = pedagogical tasks for the team and the school, OATTS = organizational and administrative tasks for the team or the school.

^a = percentages of the five categories as partitions of the 28.94% collaborative activities.

^b = percentages of the five categories as partitions of the 54.33% activities with regular teachers.

^c = percentages of the five categories as partitions of the 11.98% activities with special needs teachers.

^d = for IT, IST, and OATC mixed shows the partition with secondary tasks, for PTTS and OATTS mixed shows the partition of primary tasks, for all tasks mixed shows the partition of mixed tasks in either all activities in overall, collaborative, regular teachers or special needs teachers.

^e = percentages of all tasks in column collaborative are in relation to overall activities, percentages of all tasks in column with regular teachers and in column with special needs teachers are in relation to the 28.94% collaborative activities.

Fig. 4. Frequency of the Five Non-Mutually Exclusive Categories.

Table 3

Summary of Multilevel Models 1.3 and 1.4 (Appendix B1) Showing Effects of Collaboration Partners and the Three Collaboration Tasks on Perceived Benefit.

	β	SE	p
Fixed effects			
Intercept	-0.021	0.026	.417
SNT vs. OT	0.224	0.052	.000
RT vs. OT	0.171	0.032	.000
SNT vs. RT	0.053	0.049	.274
PT vs. ST	0.340	0.033	.000
MT vs. ST	0.166	0.015	.007
PT vs. MT	0.174	0.062	.000
No. of tasks	0.015	0.013	.224
Duration	-0.000	0.000	.420
Random effect (variance and SD)			
Person		0.268 (0.518)	
Residual		0.987 (0.993)	
Conditional R ²		0.238	
Marginal R ²		0.024	
No. of observations		5610	
No. of groups		569	

Note. For details for each model, see Appendix B1. SNT = special needs teachers, RT = regular teachers, OT = other school professionals and combinations, PT = primary tasks, ST = secondary tasks, MT = mixed tasks. β = outcome with level 1 standard deviation standardized: For categorical predictors (e.g., SNT vs. RT), the coefficient (β) indicates the expected change in the outcome relative to the variability within an individual teacher when moving from one category to the other. **Bold** = significant contrasts.

Pedagogical tasks for the team and the school (PTTS^h) and organizational and administrative tasks for the team and the school (OATTS^h) showed the strongest difference. The weaker but still significant difference indicated that teachers perceived organizational and administrative tasks for the class (OATC^h) as less beneficial than IT^h. Only individual support tasks (IST^h) were not perceived as less beneficial than IT^h.

Second, we used individual support tasks (IST^h) as the reference group. There was no significant difference between OATC^h and IST^h. The difference between PTTS^h and IST^h was significant, with PTTS^h being perceived as less beneficial. Further, the model showed significant differences between IST^h and OATTS^h, where OATTS^h was perceived as less beneficial than IST^h.

Third, we used organizational and administrative tasks for the class (OATC^h) as the reference group and compared perceived benefit to PTTS^h and OATTS^h, finding that teachers experienced both as less beneficial than OATC^h. Last, we used PTTS^h as the reference group and found no difference in perceived benefit between PTTS^h and OATTS^h.

Regarding the difference in perceived benefit between collaborative activities with different collaboration partners, this model showed the same pattern as the model with the three categories. Again, none of the covariates showed significant effects on teachers' perceived benefit of collaborative activities.

Table 4
Summary of Multilevel Models 2.1–2.4 (Appendix B2) Showing Effects of Collaboration Partners and the Five Collaboration Tasks on Perceived Benefit.

	β	SE	p
Fixed effects Level 1			
Intercept	−0.22	0.206	.411
SNT vs. OT	0.238	0.052	.000
RT vs. OT	0.162	0.033	.000
SNT vs. RT	0.076	0.051	.132
IST vs. IT	−0.089	0.047	.057
OATC vs. IT	−0.145	0.053	.007
PTTS vs. IT	−0.351	0.045	.000
OATTS vs. IT	−0.388	0.043	.000
OATC vs. IST	−0.055	0.058	.339
PTTS vs. IST	−0.262	0.052	.000
OATTS vs. IST	−0.299	0.049	.000
PTTS vs. OATC	−0.207	0.058	.000
OATTS vs. OATC	−0.243	0.054	.000
OATTS vs. PTTS	−0.037	0.046	.426
Duration	−0.000	0.000	.368
Number of tasks	−0.015	0.013	.267
Random effect (variance and SD)			
Person		0.270 (0.520)	
Residual		0.966 (0.983)	
Conditional R ²		0.238	
Marginal R ²		0.024	
No. of observations		5610	
No. of groups		596	

Note. For details for each model, see Appendix B2. SNT = special needs teachers, RT = regular teachers, OT = other school organizational and administrative tasks for the class, PTTS = pedagogical task for the team or the school, OATTS = organizational and administrative task for the team or the school. Model 2.1: Partner and task categories with OT and IT as contrasts, Model 2.2: partner and task categories with RT and IST as contrasts, Model 2.3: partner and task categories with RT and OATC as contrasts, Model 2.4: partner and task categories with RT and PTTS as contrasts. β = Outcome with level 1 standard deviation standardized: For categorical predictors (e.g., PT vs. OATTS), the coefficient (β) indicates the expected change in the standardized outcome when moving from one category to the other. **Bold** = significant contrasts.

6. Discussion

Although the extent of teacher collaboration varies across education systems, schools, and individual teachers (OECD, 2019; Liu & Benoliel, 2022), it has become an integral part of professional practice worldwide (OECD, 2024). However, previous research has produced mixed findings on teacher collaboration, including reports of negative effects (Vangrieken et al., 2015). Our study addresses two key gaps in the current understanding of teacher collaboration. First, it remains unclear to what extent collaborative activities focus on primary versus secondary tasks, and whether this distinction helps explain when collaboration is experienced as beneficial. Second, little is known about whether regular teachers experience collaboration differently when working with other regular teachers versus with special needs teachers, and whether these two constellations differ in their emphasis on primary versus secondary tasks.

One of our key findings is that nearly half of regular teachers' collaborative activities focus on secondary tasks related to school- or team-level duties, and these are perceived as less beneficial than collaboration on primary, instruction-related tasks. This is especially notable as teachers' overall non-instructional activities involve mostly primary tasks (OECD, 2019, 2024). For professional learning through collaboration—which is a precursor to adapted instruction and higher student achievement (Wullschleger et al., 2025)—this is concerning. Theory on professional learning communities (Mitchell & Sackney, 2011) suggests that collaboration contributes to teachers' professional learning through active and reflective construction of new knowledge. Active and reflective construction of new knowledge begins with surfacing tacit knowledge that underlies teachers' everyday instructional practice. Only when tacit knowledge is brought to light can it become the object of active reflection. Thus, collaboration that focuses on the primary tasks (instruction and student learning) is indispensable for such surfacing to occur.

This view is not only supported theoretically but also empirically. Studies on effective collaborative professional development have also concluded that collaboration is most effective for teachers' learning when it centers on day-to-day classroom teaching (e.g., Camburn & Han, 2017). The high prevalence of less beneficially perceived secondary duties in our data suggests that collaboration often lacks this quality of meaning and focus on the core concern of teachers, which may help explain why earlier studies have reported mixed effects on teachers' professional learning (Vangrieken et al., 2015).

This considerable proportion of secondary tasks in collaborative activities may stem from the global shift toward school governance models that emphasize both increased school autonomy and heightened accountability (Verger et al., 2024). When schools gain greater autonomy but also face stricter accountability measures without centralized support for secondary tasks, the workload on staff, particularly in relation to these secondary tasks, tends to rise (Thompson et al., 2022). In education systems that require extensive

documentation, compliance, and reporting, such as South Korea and Malaysia, administrative burdens are higher, which can increase in stress and burnout (Ani et al., 2025) and reduce the time available for teachers' primary tasks (Kim, 2019), potentially undermining instructional quality and student learning. Conversely, in systems that grant high collegial autonomy over primary tasks while providing strong centralized support for secondary tasks, such as Finland, the balance between instructional and administrative work tends to favor primary tasks. This arrangement allows teachers to exercise autonomy primarily in areas that are professionally meaningful to them, while reducing the burden of decision-making in areas they perceive as less important, which may, in turn, foster more effective professional learning and a decrease in workload (OECD, 2014; Paulsrud & Wermke, 2020). Our second research question addressed how task types differ between collaboration among regular teachers and collaboration with special needs teachers. The data indicate that collaborative activities with special needs teachers are significantly more focused on primary tasks. This reflects the special needs teachers' distinct role as their responsibilities are closely tied to supporting individual students during instructional time. In addition, collaboration between regular and special needs teachers often occurs before or after joint instructional periods, when both are present in the classroom with the same students. Such greater task interdependence has been shown to foster more intensive learning activities during collaboration (Runhaar et al., 2014). When teachers share responsibility for addressing the same instructional challenges, collaboration becomes necessary to coordinate actions and align understandings. This necessity creates a starting point for active and reflective inquiry into the tacit knowledge, values, and beliefs that underlie practice, thereby potentially supporting the construction of new professional knowledge (Mitchell & Sackney, 2011). Among regular teachers, high task interdependence is less common since they typically work with different groups of students; this reduces their interdependence on primary tasks and, in turn, could lead to less collaboration on those tasks.

A more detailed look at collaboration on primary tasks with special needs teachers revealed that significantly more time is spent on individual student support than on instructional planning. However, inclusive education should prioritize the participation of pupils with special needs in regular instruction, provided quality is maintained (Buli-Holmberg & Jeyaprabhan, 2016). Strengthening collaboration on instructional planning could improve teaching for all pupils. This is particularly relevant as special needs teachers are often present for only a few lessons per week. Joint planning on instruction could allow regular teachers to benefit from their colleagues' expertise and apply it across all lessons, fostering better integration of pupils with special needs (Paulsrud & Nilholm, 2023).

However, our data also reveals that teachers do not perceive collaboration with special needs teachers per se as more beneficial than collaboration with other regular teachers; this could indicate that leveraging diverse, and potentially conflicting, perspectives is not straightforward.

Our findings have several implications for future research on teacher collaboration. First, they highlight the importance of systematically considering the full range of task types in collaboration. Distinguishing between primary and secondary tasks is essential for understanding their perceived benefit. This distinction may be particularly relevant for studies comparing educational systems across countries or organizational structures across schools. Second, research should further examine the conditions at the personal (e.g., need for autonomy), team (e.g., cognitive and affective climate), and organizational levels (e.g., leadership) that shift collaborative activities toward primary tasks. One promising approach could be to adapt school structures so that regular teachers share more responsibility for the same students or even spend more time together in the same classroom. Increased task interdependence and shared responsibility might lead to more collaboration on primary tasks, which in turn could foster professional learning and enhance instructional quality. Third, while greater interdependence can promote more productive collaboration, it may also heighten conflict when diverse roles and perspectives are involved (Paulsrud & Nilholm, 2023). This underscores the need to study the emotional and cognitive team climates that enable teachers to constructively engage with divergent viewpoints (Mitchell & Sackney, 2011).

7. Limitations and conclusion

Large-scale international studies have shown that collaboration is a fundamental aspect of teachers' professional practice. Our study highlights the diverse tasks in which teachers engage during collaboration in their non-instructional work time and relates these tasks to teachers' perception of the benefits of collaboration.

Several limitations of the study should be acknowledged. First, the use of a single-item measure for perceived benefit reduces participant burden, but it may lack the depth needed to fully capture the nuances of teachers' perception of certain tasks. Second, the categorization of tasks into non-mutually exclusive categories for frequency analysis and into mutually exclusive categories for multilevel models complicates interpretation of the results. Future similar study designs should make it easier to identify the main tasks on which teachers collaborate. Third, we did not collect additional information on other dimensions of the collaborative activities, such as the degree of interdependence, whether the settings were formal or informal, or the characteristics of the conversations between teachers. This missing depth might also explain why our models account for only a small portion of the variance in perceived benefit. Fourth, our analysis focused on the collaborative activities of regular teachers and their perceptions of these activities. Future research should aim to incorporate perspectives of regular teachers, special needs teachers, and other school professionals also using mixed method approaches. Integrating qualitative methods would allow researchers to identify types of tasks more precisely, capture nuances of interdependence and conversational quality, and thereby explain mechanisms behind perceived benefit more precisely. Fifth, our analysis was conducted before the COVID-19 pandemic. As Azorín and Fullan (2022) note, the pandemic may have exposed weaknesses in school collaboration, and subsequent changes in structures and norms could affect the relevance of our findings today. Lastly, in our analysis we did not include random slopes or person means of task frequencies at Level 2. As a result, our approach only allowed us to examine differences between collaborative activities, not between individuals. Further studies should further explore individual (e.g., attitude toward inclusion), contextual (e.g., national school policies), and situational (e.g., specific periods within a school year) aspects explaining differences in frequency and perceived benefit of the tasks and the collaboration partner in teachers'

collaborative activities.

Despite these limitations, our findings clearly indicate that a high proportion of less beneficial secondary tasks in teacher collaboration raises concerns about its overall benefit. Furthermore, our results show that collaborating with special needs teachers instead of other regular teachers does not inherently lead to more beneficial outcomes. However, depending on the roles involved, the balance between primary and secondary tasks can shift substantially, which in turn contributes to greater perceived benefits.

Regarding practical implications for policymakers, school leaders, teacher educators, and teachers, it is essential to monitor how teachers allocate their limited time and energy during collaboration in non-instructional work time, particularly with respect to primary and secondary tasks. For instance, school leaders could provide stronger administrative support for organizing school events and managing resources, while policymakers could reduce or streamline reporting and documentation requirements to help prevent an overload of secondary tasks. Moreover, teachers, potentially supported by teacher educators, could critically review their existing collaboration routines and, if necessary, introduce more formally scheduled collaboration with clear agendas, structured time management, and guiding questions. In addition, training school and middle leaders in leadership approaches that emphasize instructional development (e.g., instructional leadership) could help ensure that collaboration remains focused on teachers' core responsibility: teaching and supporting student learning.

Swiss National Science Foundation Grant 100,019_175,872/1 funded this work.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this paper, the authors used ChatGPT versions 5.0–5.2 to improve language and readability, in combination with language proofreading by a native English speaker. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data. R Code will be made available on request.

Funding

Swiss National Science Foundation Grant 100,019_175,872/1 funded this work.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Flurin Gotsch: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Beat Rechsteiner:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Investigation, Data curation. **Miriam Compagnoni:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Andrea Wullschleger:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Investigation, Data curation. **Katharina Maag Merki:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.ijer.2026.102993](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2026.102993).

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